

Partnership for the Assessment of Risks from Chemicals

Deliverable D3.2 PARC's Communication and Dissemination Strategy WP3

D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 2

Technical References

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Responsible author(s)	Roser Gasol, EEA, roser.gasol@eea.europa.eu Tamás Szigeti, NPHC, szigeti.tamas@nnk.gov.hu
Co-authors	T3.2 partners, WP3 co-leaders, PARC CT Isabel Moura, APA, isabel.moura@apambiente.pt Zoi Mousia, EFET, zmousia@efet.gr Foteini Tzoumanika, EFET, ftzoumanika@efet.gr Nikolaos Katerelos, EFET, nkaterelos@efet.gr Afroditi Avgeri, EFET, aavgeri@efet.gr Ana Patrícia Lopes Virgolino, FMUL, avirgolino@medicina.ulisboa.pt <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 2px;">Ioanna Aggelopoulou, GCSL, i.aggelopoulou@aade.gr Vassiliki Nikou, GCSL, v.nikou@aade.gr</div> Urska Kolar, NIJZ, urska.kolar@nijz.si Lucika Perharic, NIJZ, Lucija.Perharic@nijz.si Sture Rolfheim-Bye, STAMI, Sture.Rolfheim.Bye@stami.no Steen Mollerup, STAMI, Steen.Mollerup@stami.no Kari Larssen-Aas, STAMI, kari.larssen-aas@stami.no Stephan Böse-O'Reilly, UMIT, stephan.boese-oreilly@umit-tirol.at
Reviewers	Basile Cazalis de Fondouce, ANSES, basile.cazalisdefondouce@anses.fr Hans Reynders, dOMG, hans.reynders@vlaanderen.be Aglia Koutsodimou, GCSL, a.koutsodimou@aade.gr Eugenia Dessipri, GCSL, e.desipri@aade.gr Maria João Silva, INSA, m.joao.silva@insa.min-saude.pt Sónia Namorado, INSA, sonia.namorado@insa.min-saude.pt Henriqueta Louro, INSA, Henriqueta.Louro@insa.min-saude.pt Ana Isabel Cañas Portilla, ISCIII, acanas@isciii.es Lina Wendt – Rasch, KEMI, Lina.Wendt-Rasch@kemi.se Veronika Gál, NPHC, gal.veronika@nnk.gov.hu

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
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Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 3

	Nicole Bandow, UBA, Nicole.Bandow@uba.de Maria Uhl, EAA, maria.uhl@umweltbundesamt.at Lucile Bielská, RECETOX, lucie.bielska@recetox.muni.cz
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¹ PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document history

Version	Date	Reviewer name/institution	Short description of changes
1	14.10.2023	CT and WP3 co-leaders	Feedback integrated
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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 4

Abstract

The PARC Communication and Dissemination Strategy outlines the strategy for dissemination and communication activities carried out during PARC.

Its goal is to provide a framework for effective external communication of the partnership with stakeholders at local, national and EU level to nurture the uptake of PARC results and knowledge.

In this document, we intend to identify simple key messages from the outputs of the project suited for clearly-defined target audience.

On this basis, it presents the select tailor-made communication products, tools and communication channels to be leveraged in order to achieve the objectives of the partnership.

In addition, it proposes reachable yet ambitious KPI to measure, monitor and improve the efficiency of the communication activities conducted in PARC.

The PARC Communication and Dissemination Strategy also aims to shape the strategy in order to maximise the partnership's impact through widely-accessible and easily-reusable results for all.

It also explores how to drive engagement with the stakeholders and EU citizens.

This deliverable will be instrumental for the development of a common understanding and a common vision of PARC both within and outside of the partnership.

Key Words

- Communication
- Synergies
- Dissemination
- Stakeholder
- Target audience
- Social media
- Engagement
- Strategy
- Raising awareness

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 5

Table of contents

Technical References.....	2
Document history	3
List of abbreviations	6
1. Introduction.....	7
2. Management and coordination of the communication strategy	8
3. Current situation: SWOT analysis from the communication perspective	8
4. PARC goals and communication objectives.....	10
4.1 Horizon Europe framework and PARC	10
4.2 PARC objectives	11
4.3 PARC communication objectives.....	12
5. Expected impacts of the PARC project	14
6. Defining our audience: who are we talking to?.....	16
6.1 A stakeholder mapping and engagement plan.....	16
6.2 Target audience	19
7. Key messages	21
8. Communication tools.....	24
9. How to make full use of the results	27
10. Engagement with key stakeholders.....	29
10.1 Engagement with the PARC Governing Board.....	29
10.2 Engagement with the National Hubs	29
10.3 Engagement with the Stakeholder Forum	29
10.4 Engagement with citizens	30
11. Social media strategy	30
12. Media strategy	32
13. Communication workplan.....	33
14. Risk communication.....	34

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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This partnership has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101057014

D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 6

15.	<i>Monitoring and evaluation</i>	35
16.	<i>External communication rules, policies and procedures</i>	39
16.1	Rules for external communication	39
16.2	Policies for external communication	41
17.	<i>Internal communication plan</i>	41

List of abbreviations

<p>AWPs: Annual Work Plans CORDIS: Community Research and Development Information Service CT: PARC Coordination Team (ANSES) EC: European Commission EC DGs: European Commission Directorates-General EOSC: European Open Science Cloud EU: European Union FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable GB: Governing Board GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation HBM: Human Biomonitoring HBM4EU: Human Biomonitoring Initiative for Europe HRP: Horizon Results Platform KPIs: Key Performance Indicators KSOs: Key Strategic Orientations</p>	<p>MB: PARC Management Board NGOs: Non-Governmental Organizations NGRA: Next Generation Risk Assessment NHs: National Hubs NHCPs: National Hub Contact Points OO: Operational Objectives PARC: Partnership for the Assessment of Risk from Chemicals RA: Risk Assessment R&D: Research and Development R&I: Research and Innovation RM: Risk Management SF: Stakeholder Forum SMEs: Small Medium-sized Enterprises SO: Specific Objectives S2PD: Science to Policy Dialogue UNEP: United Nations Environment Program WHO: World Health Organization WP: Work Package</p>
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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 7

1. Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to outline the strategy for dissemination and communication activities carried out during PARC.

The communication and dissemination strategy is structured in sections addressing the different aspects that a communication plan may focus on: the strategy from the project to the external audiences, including the key messages, the communication tools and the elements needed to evaluate and measure the outreach of the communication strategy, as well as the basis for a proper internal communication between the project partners.

Dissemination activities will be aligned with major milestones to maximise the impacts of the project and in strong interaction with all the other work packages.

The main objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy are:

- to ensure an effective communication of the project messages, activities and results at local, national, regional and EU level
- to identify clear and simple messages from the outputs of the project
- to identify and map appropriate target groups to whom the key messages will be addressed
- to design and implement a wide range of tailor-made communication products using different tools and communication channels
- to manage the social media accounts (Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram and Twitter)
- to identify key performance indicators (KPIs) for dissemination, useful to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the activities conducted and monitor them accordingly
- to illustrate how the project will cooperate with other EC-funded projects and related initiatives and partnerships
- to make the results of the project accessible, ensuring that they can be used by others and maximise the project's impact, by defining the dissemination and exploitation activities
- to assist PARC partners to correctly implement the communication strategy.

PARC's dissemination actions aim at communicating the project's objectives and results to a wide audience by promoting the adoption of the project's results and demonstrating its impact, as well as by facilitating the exchange of information and the interaction not only with other related projects and initiatives but also with activities in industry, academia, and society as a whole.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 8

2. Management and coordination of the communication strategy

Work Package WP3 “Synergies, collaboration and awareness” is responsible for the dissemination of PARC results and will coordinate this task at a consortium level. Specifically, task 3.2 co-leaders are in charge of coordinating the communication, dissemination and awareness activities.

Due to the role in consolidating, communication and disseminating results, the task 3.2 co-leaders, the European Environment Agency (EEA) and the National Public Health Centre in Hungary (NPHC) together with many partners within this task, will draw on the outputs of all other work packages (WPs). At the same time, they will deliver services to the other WPs, by producing communication products.

Content to be included in targeted communication products will be developed in collaboration with the WPs involved in producing data and research outputs. Task 3.2 co-leaders will provide support to the development and design of communication products, as well as to the formatting and editing of products. They will also coordinate the work of the partners involved in these activities.

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy will be closely linked to each Annual Work Plan (AWP) of the PARC project and will be updated to ensure that communication and dissemination activities support the implementation of each AWP.

3. Current situation: SWOT analysis from the communication perspective

SWOT stands for strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats.

A *strength* is a resource or capacity that can be used effectively to achieve the project objective. “What are our advantages in this situation?”, “What do we do well?” or “What do other people see as our strength here?”

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 9

A *weakness* is a limitation, fault or defect in the particular product, service or issue that may be the reason for our communication plan: “What could we improve in this?”, “What do we do badly?”, or “What should we avoid?”

An *opportunity* is a favourable situation in our project, often a trend or a change of some kind or an overlooked need that increases the relevance or effectiveness of the project in question.

A *threat* is a danger or menace in our project. Often threats are ignored until they become major problems. For instance, threats can be identified by looking at the obstacles faced.

<p>Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication/dissemination team with different competences and backgrounds • Successful implementation of the previous project HBM4EU, namely at the communication level • Dealing with a very important topic with clear impact on the society and clear need for changes in legislation • Development of a structured communication plan for a wide dissemination of the project at local, national and EU levels • Project-oriented management of the PARC project and work plans prepared on annual basis and detailing the planned activities that allow for a clear and comprehensive overview of project output, result, and deliverable production and timing 	<p>Weakness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subject area very complex and technical • Project not well known in all the different sectors concerned in all European countries • Timing of availability of project results affect communication activities and message formulation • Bureaucracy and lengthy administrative processes • Complex approval decision-making
<p>Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishing new networks and strengthening the cooperation between the academic world in the field of chemical risk assessment • Possibility to reach all 28 participating countries and the EC • Press media coverage • Online presence • Technology can work in the project’s favour 	<p>Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific topic that will hardly reach a wider public and that is properly understood • Data sharing and privacy policy issues • Lack of successful stakeholder engagement • Conflicting interests among stakeholders and among partners could delay or hinder dissemination of results. • Lots of coordination work and follow-up due to the involvement of many partners

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 10

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use data visualization and storytelling approach to tell PARC’s story • Dissemination of project results in different contexts: project partners, scientific community, policy makers, general public and other stakeholders • Stakeholder Forum involvement as a key player for dissemination of PARC’s results • Creating and strengthening collaborations with national and regional science communication groups 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Results not available at the time that the communication products need to be delivered • Citizens’ limited trust in chemical risk assessment and risk management processes • Elections in each region may change the composition of the political apparatus and thus change the responsiveness of regional politicians to the project objectives during the project. • Too little attention paid to the partnership, as other burning issues and challenges might occupy the attention of policy makers and the public
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4. PARC goals and communication objectives

Horizon Europe is the EU’s key funding programme for research and innovation under which the PARC is funded. This section provides a brief overview on the strategic objectives of the Horizon Europe programme and the PARC project as well as a description of the communication objectives in relation to the PARC objectives and at societal, EU policy and project levels.

4.1 Horizon Europe framework and PARC

The policy priorities and the expected impact for Horizon Europe are described in the [Strategic Plan](#). The first Strategic Plan sets out the key strategic orientations for the targeting of investments in the programme's first four years (2021-2024). The Strategic Plan aims to promote consistency between the work programmes, EU and national priorities and to achieve continuity and coherence of funding measures.

The following four key strategic orientations (KSO) were identified in the first Strategic Plan:

- A. promoting an open strategic autonomy by leading the development of key digital, enabling and emerging technologies, sectors and value chains to accelerate and steer the digital and green transitions through human-centred technologies and innovations;
- B. restoring Europe’s ecosystems and biodiversity, and managing sustainably natural resources to ensure food security and a clean and healthy environment;

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 11

- C. making Europe the first digitally enabled circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy through the transformation of its mobility, energy, construction and production systems;
- D. creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society, prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health care, and empowering all citizens to act in the green and digital transitions.

The key strategic orientations of the Horizon Europe programme are reflected in the objectives of the PARC. PARC contributes to the goals of “Living and working in a health-promoting environment” Calls, working towards the KSO-D ‘Creating a more resilient, inclusive and democratic European society’ of Horizon Europe’s Strategic Plan 2021-2024. Research and innovation supported under this destination should contribute to the impact area ‘A resilient EU prepared for emerging threats’ and to the following expected impact set out in the Strategic Plan for the health cluster: ‘living and working environments are health-promoting and sustainable thanks to better understanding of environmental, occupational, social and economic determinants of health’. In addition, research and innovation supported under this destination could also contribute to the following impact areas: ‘Good health and high-quality accessible health care’, ‘Climate change mitigation and adaptation’, and ‘Clean and healthy air, water and soil’. PARC specifically falls under the call ‘Partnership in health’.

4.2 PARC objectives

The objectives of PARC have been described in the Project proposal – Technical description (Part B). The general objective of PARC is to consolidate and strengthen the EU's R&I capacity for chemical RA to protect human health and the environment. In total 13 realistic, measurable, achievable and verifiable operational objectives (OO) were defined under three specific objectives (SO).

The specific and the operational objectives are:

SO1. EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA.

OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC.

OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH).

OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy.

OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge.

OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives.

OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen’s understanding/ awareness of chemical RA.

SO2. European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals RA.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 12

OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes.

OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes.

OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA.

OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake.

SO3. European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA.

OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.

OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.

OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.

4.3 PARC communication objectives

Both strategic and tactical communication efforts are needed in order to share a common understanding of PARC. This will contribute to achieving the vision and ambition of PARC.

Given the structure societal impact, EU-policy and PARC-project, the objectives-hierarchy are as follows:

Objective level	Communication goal	Comments
Societal level	To ensure that the impact of PARC is recognised as one of the important accelerators of the development of new technologies and sectors like the chemical RA and RM, and crucial in steering the green transition.	<i>Reflecting Horizon</i>
	To ensure that citizens are empowered in the green transition as well as contributing to a more resilient, inclusive, and responsive Europe.	<i>Reflecting Horizon</i>
	To ensure a common and shared understanding of what PARC is about and why PARC has been established.	<i>Reflecting ambition and vision</i>
	To continuously promote PARCs different activities, covering all the work done in the WPs by making the results of the project accessible.	<i>Reflecting ambition and vision</i>
	Raise public awareness and public literacy with regards to chemical exposure, providing insights into possible	<i>SO1, SO2 and SO3</i>

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 13

	behavioural changes that can reduce chemical exposure and improve health and well-being.	
	Ensure trust and trust ability towards PARC and the knowledge provision from PARC.	SO1, SO2 and SO3
	To ensure that all the key research findings are communicated with the society in an understandable and accessible language.	SO1, SO2 and SO3
	Engage with societal actors and public focus groups to better understand societal concerns regarding chemical exposure and awareness of chemical RA.	SO1, SO2 and SO3
EU Policy level	Build a bridge between science and policy through continuous dialogue and engagement between individuals involved in cutting edge scientific research and individuals involved in all stages of chemical risk assessment and management.	SO1, SO2 and SO3
	To communicate the priorities for R&I in chemical RA, and RM with key stakeholders including regulators, national chemical RA and RM authorities, policymakers, scientists etc...	SO1, SO2
	Communicate effectively with target audiences to ensure policy uptake.	
	To achieve a change of practice (in regulatory uptake and use) and through implementation of new and innovative chemical RA methods.	SO1, SO3 <i>Knowledge production and new methods does not necessarily change practice and needs to be addressed continuously to achieve a step-by-step change.</i>
	To ensure that models and innovative concepts are contributing to S2PD the need to be both accessible, easily understandable, and useable.	SO2
	To raise awareness of, knowledge about, and the use of the tools facilitating knowledge uptake.	SO3
	Strengthen the perceived trust and trust ability in the partners involved in the production and dissemination/distribution of the different tools.	SO3
	PARC Project Level	Foster stakeholder engagement in PARC, so that stakeholders can contribute to disseminate and exploit our results in their own activities as well as promoting synergies amongst all.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 14

	To ensure a shared understanding of, and approach to, FAIR data practices among PARC partners by addressing both the added value and the importance of “our shared political and social mission”.	SO2
	To ensure that the training programmes are available any potential stakeholder interested in the topics.	SO3
	To facilitate the exchange of information for all PARC members.	SO3

5. Expected impacts of the PARC project

The communication and dissemination strategy will contribute to the delivery of a number of impacts expected from the PARC project. The PARC project will involve several structures which will play an important role in helping towards the achievement of the expected impacts, namely at the policy/societal, scientific, and economic levels.

Policy/societal impact

First network of more than 200 European, cross-sectorial public partners working on risk assessment for chemicals at national and/or European level

Scientific impact

Collaboration between networks of partners working in different areas, to construct a common approach and the sharing of data based on FAIR principles

Economic impact

Development of approach to support innovation in chemistry while reducing risks for health and the environment

The **policy/societal impacts** of PARC will be the endorsement of innovative approaches in chemical RA at national, EU and international level and to reinforce the citizens, workers, and stakeholders' trust in science and how regulations protect humans and the environment. The communication and

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 15

dissemination strategy will contribute to the achievement of the destination 2 ‘Living and working in a health-promoting environment’ expected impacts by enabling policymakers and regulators to be better informed about chemicals as environmental, socio-economic and occupational risk and health promoting factors by increasing awareness and understanding of scientific evidence and chemical RA procedures. Through the communication of PARC activities and dissemination of results, PARC will also contribute to citizens’ understanding of environmental and health issues, the measures to address them, and of the related policies and regulations to protect them and their environment. Concerning the national scale, the NHs will be of utmost relevance for the dissemination of PARC interests and outputs and to raise citizens’ awareness. To assess success, number of interactions with citizens/stakeholders will be used as indicators. This level will be addressed by communicating and disseminating project data including reports in non-scientific media, outreach/awareness raising activities, interactions with stakeholders, website/social media use.

The **scientific impact** of PARC will come from the achievement of PARC’s SO2: ‘European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals risk assessment’. To promote PARC at national, EU and international levels, fundamental scientific results will be communicated through appropriate channels such as publications in peer-reviewed journals, presentations at international conferences and workshops. By disseminating knowledge through systematic application of open science, R&I activities will be able to deliver results and knowledge corresponding to the needs of end-users. This way, PARC will contribute to the improvement of the protection of environmental and citizen’s health, and awareness of citizens and professionals about risks of chemical exposures.

The **economic impact** of PARC will result from the achievement of PARC’s SO3: ‘European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical risk assessment’. The communication and dissemination strategy will contribute to the delivery of this objective by fostering communication across the stakeholder groups.

The contribution of PARC to the defined outcomes and wider impacts, and the activities implemented to maximize these, will be followed closely throughout the Partnership to measure its performance and ultimately to provide a robust justification for the long-term sustainability of PARC’s activities. PARC’s impact pathway is defined in its monitoring frame to provide a qualitative and quantitative-based indication of the scale and significance of PARC’s contribution to the expected outcomes and impacts.

Under task 1.3. ‘Impact evaluation and Monitoring of the performance indicators of the Partnership’, the set of indicators, including baselines and clear targets, will be further developed, with PARC’s different boards and stakeholders, containing output, outcome and impact (quantitative and

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 16

qualitative) indicators linked to operational, specific and general objective(s) to ensure their relevance for evaluating the progress of the results, and specifically the political, scientific and social impact of the Partnership.

6. Defining our audience: who are we talking to?

6.1 A stakeholder mapping and engagement plan

Our strategy for engaging with stakeholders aims to promote their active participation in PARC. Engagement implies that the targets do not merely receive information, but that they contribute to, understand and exploit the results. PARC stakeholders will have the chance to influence the prioritisation and decision-making process and shape outcomes, increasing their capacity to exploit our results.

Stakeholder engagement approaches depend on the level of interest and the level of influence of the stakeholder. The higher the influence and the interest of the stakeholder are, the greater the investment in their participation should be. Figure 1 below illustrates the relationship between stakeholder influence and the investment in stakeholder engagement.

Certain stakeholders can act as multipliers of PARC messages. By reaching out to their constituencies and to the public, stakeholders have the potential to disseminate our messages to a larger audience and to increase our visibility. European level stakeholders with extensive networks in the Member States can access audiences at the national level. Such stakeholders can also gather input from their constituencies to feed into project activities, so increasing the credibility and legitimacy of PARC.

National Hub Contact Points should be contacted to identify key stakeholders at national level. On this basis, we will build a list of stakeholders in the partner countries.

Figure 1: Relationship between stakeholder influence and approaches to stakeholder engagement: ‘joint ownership’ means high influence and high interest, ‘committed’ – high influence, low interest, ‘engaged’ – low influence and high interest, and ‘aware’ – low influence and low interest.

D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 17

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 18

This is why a stakeholder mapping is a crucial part of the strategy, which is a collaborative process of research, debate, and discussion that draws from multiple perspectives to determine a key list of stakeholders across the entire stakeholder spectrum. Mapping can be broken down into four phases:

1. Identifying: listing relevant groups, organisations, and people
2. Analysing: understanding stakeholder perspectives and relevance
3. Mapping: visualizing relationships to objectives and other stakeholders
4. Prioritizing: ranking stakeholder relevance and identifying issues

Figure 2. Stakeholders mapping

In this way, communications objectives can be clearly identified, and the messages can be tailored according to the needs of the external stakeholder groups. Based on their potential influence on and interest in PARC, four categories has been identified.

- The category of 'Key Players' should potentially have high interest and high influence, therefore are clearly those we want to spend the most time communicating with and manage closely.
- The category of 'Keep in Radar' has potentially low influence on and interest in the project, therefore we only need to monitor, so we will devote little time to these stakeholders.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 19

- The category of ‘Keep Satisfied’ has potentially high influence and low interest and the category of ‘Keep Informed’ has potentially high interest and low influence, so with those two groups of stakeholders we do need to communicate our results.

It is likely that some of these audiences will become more or less influential and have a greater or lesser interest in our project over time and depending on their interaction with us.

An exercise on mapping our stakeholders will be done in the first year by WP3 in close collaboration with the Coordination Team and WP (co) leaders in order to build an inventory of stakeholders. We will also involve the Stakeholder Forum with this exercise.

6.2 Target audience

To achieve the main project objectives and ensure that our results are exploited and generate impact, we will need to disseminate our outputs and actively engage with a broad range of end users at national and international levels. These end users can be categorised under the following groups: researchers, policymakers, EU authorities/regulators in the field of chemical risk assessment, citizens, risk assessors and managers, industry, consumers and worker associations and many other groups indirectly involved.

When thinking who our audience is, the following questions matter:

- Do you have one or multiple audiences?
- Are there any communication barriers such as language or trust?
- What are their values and priorities?
- What might you have in common with the audience?

It is also important to decide who is the most influential. A small number of powerful advocates can make big things happen. We will identify that group. The smaller and more well-defined a target group is, the easier it is to develop focussed communication that will really influence them. Nowadays people are influenced by ‘people like us’ more than they are influenced by voices of authority.

Level	Audience	Communication tools and channels needs
Political level	Regulatory bodies National chemical RA and RM authorities EC EC DGs Policy makers	Policy briefs / newsletters Press releases Conferences / webinars Reports Website

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 20

	<p>Members of the European Parliament and national members of Parliament</p> <p>National ministries responsible for public health, environment, labour, occupational safety and research</p> <p>Parliamentary Working Group</p> <p>Think tanks</p> <p>National Hubs contact points</p> <p>Regional institutions</p> <p>International organisations (WHO, UNEP....)</p>	<p>Social media</p> <p>Face to face meetings</p>
Scientific level	<p>International experts</p> <p>International bodies</p> <p>Scientific advisors</p> <p>Scientific societies and associations</p> <p>Scientific community</p> <p>Universities and research groups</p> <p>National research institutes in the field of public health and environment</p> <p>R&D groups in industry/private companies</p> <p>Other European projects and initiatives in the field of risk assessment and chemical safety</p> <p>Other relevant European networks (i.e., NRLs, metrology etc)</p>	<p>Scientific papers</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Conferences / workshops</p> <p>Webinars</p> <p>Science Digest Newsletter</p> <p>Network meetings</p> <p>Brief on tools developed</p>
Industry level	<p>EU Industry representatives and associations Including members of SF (Stakeholder Forum)</p> <p>SMEs in the field of chemistry</p> <p>Health insurance industry and the health sector</p> <p>Start-ups in the field related to chemicals, health and environment</p> <p>Trade unions</p>	<p>SF meetings, other stakeholder groups formed in the framework of various project activities</p> <p>Brief on tools developed</p>
Innovation level	<p>R&D Departments from both public and private sector</p>	<p>Webinars / conferences</p> <p>Website</p> <p>Stakeholder Forum</p> <p>Newsletters / policy briefs</p> <p>Videos</p> <p>Scientific papers</p>
Societal level	<p>Health professionals including gynaecologists and paediatricians (to reach pregnant women)</p> <p>Schools (to reach children and teenagers)</p> <p>Consumers' protection agencies</p> <p>Consumers</p>	<p>Website (and especially the citizen's microsite)</p> <p>Videos / visuals</p> <p>Webinars</p> <p>Leaflets, factsheet and infographics</p>

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 21

	Citizens associations (including vulnerable groups) and general public NGOs PARC survey participants Media	Press released / media interaction Key messages – scientific outcomes
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7. Key messages

To achieve the highest impact, ideally, one should package a science message based on the audience and the goal.

At this point, it makes sense to limit the number of key messages to keep the vision of the project clear. Later on, when the dissemination of the deliverables and results will be at full speed, all our communication products will need to be tailored to the target audience with a clear and concise messaging.

The proposition may be supported by the top-line messages - the most important points we wish to get across to the audience. Crucial questions to consider at this stage are:

- What are the key messages we wish to communicate?
- How do these messages relate to and support each other?
- Are these messages short, jargon-free, concise and meaningful?

Project objectives	Communication objectives	Target group	Messages
SO1:EU and national risk assessors and regulatory entities come together with the scientific community in a cross-disciplinary network to set priorities for R&I in chemical RA			
OO1: Set-up and operate a high-level group to strategically steer PARC	Promote the uptake of PARC results	Governing Board	PARC is vital to the empowerment of all citizens in the green transition as well as contributing to a more resilient, inclusive, and responsive Europe.
OO2: Expand long-term sustainable network of National Hubs (NH)	Influence behaviour and also promote the uptake of	National Hubs Regulatory bodies Policy makers	PARC will provide ad-hoc evidence-based strategies and tools for policymakers

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 22

	PARC results at national, regulatory and policy level		and regulators as well as active engagement.
OO3: Define common R&I strategies with transparent criteria and a prioritisation strategy	Increase understanding on evidence based, exposure & drugs	Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	Strategies employed to develop PARC are evidence based. Focus of PARC activities are reactive to identified regulatory priorities and new challenges.
OO4: Actively foster regulatory uptake of PARC knowledge.	Influence behaviour (and so regulatory actions)	Regulatory bodies Policy makers Parliamentary WG Think tanks	An update on legislation is crucial for implementation of NGRA.
OO5: Promote cooperation with other R&I initiatives.	Raise visibility of PARC project	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	PARC is harvesting the knowledge of a broad scientific community.
OO6: Communicate & disseminate PARC knowledge to increase citizen's understanding/awareness of chemical RA.	Raise awareness of chemical risk assessment and influence behaviour	General public, Professional risk communicators, health professionals	Next generation of risk assessment will elevate citizen and consumer protection.
SO2.			
European and national RA entities and their scientific networks carry out a joint R&I programme to respond to the agreed priorities in chemicals RA			
OO7: Develop/ implement annual R&I work programmes			
OO8: Develop monitoring capacity by extending the HBM platform created in HBM4EU and supporting the provision of environmental and multisource data for regulatory purposes.	Increase understanding	Regulatory bodies Policy makers Parliamentary WG Think tanks Consumers' protection agencies Consumers	PARC is a continuation and extension of HBM4EU, it generates knowledge to inform risk assessment, the safe management of chemicals and so protect human health and the environment in Europe.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 23

		Citizens associations NGOs	
OO10: Implement FAIR data practices and enhance innovation in complex data analysis for RA.	Increased understanding	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	Principles of FAIR data are applied to all the steps in PARC activities.
OO12: Develop models and innovative concepts for RA and deliver toolboxes to promote their acceptability and uptake.	Raise visibility	Regulatory bodies Policy makers Parliamentary WG Think tanks	PARC contributes to preventing negative effects of hazardous chemicals in the circular and sustainable production system.
SO3. European risk assessors, their scientific network and the wider stakeholder community have access to the R&I capacities required to implement innovative chemical RA.			
OO9: Develop tools to facilitate the acceptance and use of PARC results in regulatory RA processes and support (existing) standardisation and validation processes for innovative approaches to RA.	Raise visibility	Industry Including members of SF (stakeholder forum)	PARC supports innovation in chemistry while reducing risk for health and the environment.
OO11: Consolidate existing and develop new networks of laboratories and research centres.	Influence behaviour	Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	PARC operates by building up and sharing knowledge and capacities.
OO13: Build capacities by developing and carrying out training and exchange programmes in chemical RA.	Strengthen the perceived trust and trust ability in the partners involved	International experts International bodies Scientific advisors Scientific societies Scientific community	The NGRA resulting in PARC activities will be implemented by trained professionals.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 24

8. Communication tools

When profiling target groups for such a wide and heterogeneous group of end users, it is critical to **tailor** the communication products to the relevant audiences. Communication products must be made accessible and comprehensible to all target groups identified, by considering for example the technical understanding in the different socio-cultural contexts involved. The communication strategy rests on a set of coherent but differentiated communication tools, with the separate products tailored to match the needs of the different end users and audience.

The use of visuals - An extensive use of graphic design is foreseen to facilitate the understanding and memorability of messages based on complex scientific information and data. Infographics and data-visualisation are tools that combine aesthetic quality with simplicity in translating messages to target audiences. Infographics can facilitate understanding of project activities and can be used to raise awareness of the project, specifically via sharing through social media. Data visualisation can support the communication of complex data in an intuitive manner. To better deliver the message PARC partnership we will use as its communication tools in its different channels' scientific illustrations, infographics, conceptual diagrams, maps, tables and figures, animations and video clips too.

Under PARC a wide range of communication products will be developed in due course.

- **PARC Visual identity**

A new project identity will be created before December 2022, which will include: a logo package, colour of palette, templates for presentations as well as for reports, deliverables, and letters, e-mail signature and event agenda, graphic-roll out, principle design for data visualization (figures and graphs), a leaflet that will be translated in all European languages, a template for the PARC newsletter and the PARC Science Digest as well as a few interactive media design and animated communication products. In order to set a common visual graphical language for all dissemination products a PARC Visual Identity and Branding Manual will be drafted and circulated amongst all partners.

- **The PARC website**

Our PARC website www.eu-parc.eu will be the main shop window and will showcase a complete overview of the project. All partners will be requested to deliver content for the website. The working language of the website is English. There will not be internal pages, as the ANSES SharePoint will be used for storing internal documents.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 25

The website map structure draft is as follows, although there is not yet a final menu decided as we are still discussing it amongst partners:

- *About us section*: providing information about the project and the partners, including the consortium, the SF, etc...
- *What we do section*: presenting the information on mission, vision and objectives as well as the impact of the project.
- *Thematic areas section*: presenting the main activities of the project clustered in four thematic areas.
 - Research and innovation to support risk assessment
 - Tool and resources
 - Capacity building
 - Science to policy
- *Chemicals section*: providing information on the chemicals studies and the methods used.
- *News section*: communication of news and updates on PARC activities, an event or calendar section for training events might be included.
- *Synergies section*: presenting different possibilities to partner with us and collaborate.
- *Media section*: providing information such as the media kit, branding materials, logo, etc...
- *Results section*: to show the deliverables of the project per work package.
- *PARC stories*: presenting the research projects and case studies.
- *PARCOPEDIA*: a link to a password protected site.
- *Online library and resources section*: list of peer reviewed publications and links with open access data, also having the possibility to filter them by topics and different categories.
- *Outreach section*: displaying information targeting citizens.
- An improved version of the interactive maps on the European Network of [HBM Laboratory](#)

- **Newsletters**

Two types of newsletters are foreseen to be send out.

→ **PARC Newsletter**

An electronic newsletter with the highlights and updates about the project's activities and tasks as well results, deliverables, events, etc...). There will be a subscription to the newsletter.

Contact management system - The Active monitor contact management system managed by the European Environment Agency provides a dynamic contact database for sending the newsletter. It allows stakeholders to register (and unregister) electronically to receive project mailing. The application provides an easy way for users to send email newsletters, manage (and categorise) subscriber lists, and track campaign performance. Due to GDPR, it is not possible to add subscribers, so the individuals need to actively subscribe to the newsletter.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 26

All partners are expected to contribute to the content of the newsletter. Internal procedure on the writing and approval of the newsletter will be detailed in the Communication's Handbook. The six-monthly newsletter will come out alongside the project in month M8 (December 2022), M12, M18, M24, M30, M36. The newsletter will be accessible in PARC website and distributed by electronic channels such as social media.

→ **PARC Science Digest Newsletter**

In order to increase the visibility of the many peer-reviewed publications that PARC will produce amongst the different target audiences but also to digestible to non-scientific audiences, we will send clear and concise messages in an attractive format to make it easier to capture the key messages. For that purpose, the PARC Science Digest Newsletter will be designed and send out monthly. A strategy needs to be thought on how to deal with months were there are a very low number of scientific publications to cover or even none. Like the PARC Newsletter, individuals need to subscribe to the newsletter to receive it.

A series of slides on key messages from peer-reviewed publications elaborated together with the corresponding authors of the scientific publications could be implemented and disseminated on social media. To this end, once a peer reviewed publication is published, the corresponding author working closely with the WPs co-leaders will have the opportunity to submit maximum 5 key research messages to the task co-leaders 3.2 to help with the dissemination of the publication.

- **Policy briefs**

Policy briefs are a tool that gives concise, objective summaries of relevant scientific information, as well as recommendations for policymakers. They serve as a vehicle for providing evidence-based policy advice to help policymakers make informed decisions, and so these documents might be very useful for the Governing Board and other high-level decision-makers who have very limited time to review documents. Timing of publication to dovetail with relevant decision-making processes and meetings of expert groups and committees.

- **Videos**

Videos can be simply and relatively low in information, acting as a “teaser” to activate the users’ curiosity and lead them to more detailed information. Videos can assume different purposes for different users: while general public can stop on the first “step” of the exploration process, journalists and other scientists can go on finding more in-depth contents and information. We will look at the possibility to develop some promotional videos during the first year of the project. Concept note on is currently being written to suggest the development of some videos, for instance, a one-to-one interview with PARC researchers to explain their work and provide context for their achieved results.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 27

- **Scientific publications**

Scientific publications are aimed at informing academics in particular. PARC will promote scientific publications through an open access policy. Proceedings regarding the content, referencing and alerting of the consortium will be defined in the PARC Publication Policy to which the partners are required to adhere. Scientific publications will be listed on the PARC website, as well as disseminated on the Science Digest Newsletter and social media.

- **Technical reports/deliverables**

We will summarise our research results on in concise and targeted technical reports and deliverables. We will ensure that key audiences receive these reports and follow up to provide any additional clarifications.

- **Other communication products**

Other communication products we might plan and implement, although further clarification is needed, goes as follows:

- citizen's microsite,
- PARC MAGAZINE,
- exhibition.

There are also products that are not foreseen to be developed during the first couple of years, such as factsheets, research briefs, etc but we might plan them to do in years' time. With an external provider, a data-driven and audience-centric workshop showing examples applicable to PARC and a proposal will be developed. The main objective of the workshop, which will take place in June 2023 is to collect examples on information design and data visualisation to create a narrative and a compelling communication products portfolio/proposal in an array of formats to tell that story effectively to PARC audience. Afterwards we might then choose to develop new communication products.

9. How to make full use of the results

As part of dissemination and exploitation activities, PARC will be presented in scientific conferences, workshops and events. Events in general provide a channel for dialogue and communication with a range of potential end users, networking opportunities and an opportunity to make the PARC brand visible. Events attended by PARC partners will be communicated to the WP3 co-leaders and will be published on the PARC website for partners to disseminate.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 28

It is planned that PARC partners will actively participate in major international conferences and symposia and act as our ambassadors. Our results will also be communicated at conferences organised at national level, harnessing the range of languages available in our multi-cultural team and creating synergies across different partners. We will also look at possibilities to organise side events at international negotiating fora relevant to chemicals management and public health more generally.

At the same time, PARC will specifically target events and organise its own events including workshops, discussion forums, face to face meetings, etc to communicate and exchange knowledge, to keep meaningful collaborations and cooperation and to hold discussions about given subjects, with specific groups like policymakers, risk assessors and managers, industry, NGOs.... In that way, we can have a more targeted and strategic discussions helping to boost the impact of the outcomes of PARC. While creating the space to enable, identify and prioritize joint challenges and to develop strategic research and innovation agendas to tackle them in cooperation with the scientific community and ensure the use of the results in a regulatory context and foster trust and confidence.

Bringing together policymakers and researchers, key stakeholders, workers associations, NGOs and industry, in conferences, seminars and workshops are an efficient way for researchers and scientists to communicate science. These events will allow to showcase the scientific achievements of PARC, while providing an opportunity to share knowledge and network and raise awareness about PARC.

Partners websites have regular newsletter and posts on their institutional websites and social media accounts. These channels can also be used to disseminate the activities of our projects regularly. It is now widely recognised that making research results more accessible to all contributes to better and more efficient science, and to innovation in the public and private sectors. In this regard, and to disseminate and reuse scientific results, we will:

- Use initiatives such as the [Open Research Europe](#) and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) facilitated by the European Commission to submit research publications. EOSC is also part of the [European Data Strategy](#), aiming to make the EU a leader in a data-driven society.
- Update the information at the CORDIS website by the Coordination Team. This can be used by the Commission to create editorial products that increase visibility of our results towards potential partners.
- Use the Horizon Results Platform (HRP), a matchmaking tool allowing us to publish our Key Exploitable Results to promote them vis-à-vis our targeted audiences – stakeholders, policy makers, potential business partners, etc. The HRP allows beneficiaries to fully manage their result profile and make the necessary changes when needed.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 29

10. Engagement with key stakeholders

10.1 Engagement with the PARC Governing Board

The Governing Board (GB) is the overarching body of PARC that provides the highest-level strategic steering of the Partnership and brings in the political commitment for the uptake of PARC results and its sustainability. The relevant Ministries from all participating countries as well as the relevant EC DGs (RTD, GROW, ENV, SANTE, JRC) are part of the GB.

Specific communication material for PARC GB members will be designed and produced, and although the products can be similar to the content addressed to high level decision making and policymakers given the overlap, further tailoring to the GB could be pertinent.

10.2 Engagement with the National Hubs

Concerning the national scale, the NHs will be of utmost relevance for the dissemination of PARC results and to raise citizens' awareness.

National Hubs' specific communication needs will be annually collected within T2.3, then the needs of the NHCPs will be considered and further meetings with the National Hub Co-Coordinator are planned to elaborate the process. For instance, a dedicated page on the NH contact points (NHCP) on the PARC website will be devoted, a template with general information about PARC to present at national level will be distributed, a specific announcement on when the social media accounts for PARC will be activated, etc. The NHCPs will define a roadmap for activities and might include requests for specific communication materials. Likewise, we will suggest specific communication products in due course.

10.3 Engagement with the Stakeholder Forum

Based on the experience built at HBM4EU, a PARC Stakeholder Forum build-up of a maximum of 15 organisations will be selected in the field of risk assessment of chemicals, risk communication, science to public and/or science to policy interactions. They will bring the opportunity to co-create a living and sustainable Partnership, seeking both to promote and to benefit from mutual interests, needs and priorities as well as strategic and technical aspects to ensure the progress of PARC.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 30

The members of the Stakeholder Forum are expected to contribute with feedback and input, to maximise the benefits and advantages of PARC, both for achieving PARC objectives as well as for their own activities with similar objectives.

SF will interact with the PARC consortium. Other exchanges will be possible through ad hoc (online) meetings and consultations.

They can certainly support to disseminate our PARC results and so it's vital to build relationships with them.

10.4 Engagement with citizens

Targeted citizen actions should be envisaged to increase their understanding of risks related to exposure to chemicals and reinforce their trust in risk assessment and risk management processes. PARC will develop and implement representative citizen surveys and focus groups on different partner countries to create a substantial knowledge, specifically tailored for project needs and more in-depth information about citizens' perceptions and concerns about PARC-related subjects. The citizen survey will be repeated at the end of the project which will be used to monitor the effects of PARC activities outcomes and to support future activities after PARC.

Different communication tools (e.g., microsite for citizens, factsheets, short videos, etc) will be developed in PARC to increase the engagement of the European citizens.

11. Social media strategy

Social media represents an important channel for the dissemination of PARC results. At the same time, the concise nature of exchanges on social media present challenges to communicating complex, scientific knowledge. Recognising this, social media can be used to create an online buzz around specific events or publications, using tags and links to more detailed information materials.

Social media provide an opportunity to:

- promote the PARC brand and build a robust reputation
- create awareness
- inspire stakeholders and the public to engage in dialogue
- disseminate news on project results, actions and events
- enhance the recruitment of survey participants.

Golden rules for social media:

- use simple and direct language, avoiding scientific terms
- provide a context, be it graphics, a video or an image

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 31

- link to more information
- engage other scientists, influencers and journalists to promote the visibility of the project

A short social media strategy with targets, activities and work plan will be drafted by January 2023, that will be aligned with the communication strategy. The content is listed below:

1. Who (target)
2. What messages do we send, what do we communicate (connect, report, inform)?
3. Analyse the statistics
 - What's working, and what's not?
 - Who is engaging with our audience?
 - Which networks does our target audience use?
4. How: the content
 - Make it more visual
 - Make all communication consistent
 - Right format, right channel
 - Make it clear and digestible
5. Look and feel
6. Operational set-up
7. Paid media: social media Ads
8. Measure our performance
9. Provisional targets
10. Social media campaigns
11. Social media kit

The social media accounts created for the European [Human Biomonitoring Initiative for Europe](#) (HBM4EU) will be converted into the PARC social media channels. We would like not to lose the followers achieved so far during the previous project, as the HBM4EU audience overlaps the PARC one. A digital activation plan on how to smoothly transit from HBM4EU to PARC will be planned and implemented by December 2022. In total, the HBM4EU social media accounts have: 946 followers in Twitter, 450 in Facebook, 735 in LinkedIn and 149 in Instagram. Regarding the You Tube channel, HBM4EU used a playlist embedded in the European Environment Agency's You Tube.

A social media editorial calendar will be populated based on the input from the Consortium amongst the 4 partners within Task 2.3 responsible for developing and managing the project's social media presence to plan monthly the post to be posted on social media.

To track the performance on social media, we will:

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 32

- Use Insights which is part of Facebook to get access to the Facebook Page statistics
- YouTube has its own statistics tool called YouTube Analytics. By default, there is only one user connected to a YouTube account but by connecting the YouTube account to a Google+ page, we can add multiple users to the account by adding them as manager to the Google+ page.
- Instagram only allows for one user per account, so we need to share the login details. Instagram does not include any statistics tools, so a third-party tool is needed.
- Twitter offers a comprehensive analytics tool via analytics.twitter.com.

Once the metrics have been collected through the chosen tools the evaluation questions should be revisited to map these data sources and review them against set targets and the scope of our target audience.

Partners should follow our accounts and tag PARC when possible, using the official hashtags such as #EU_PARC.

12. Media strategy

Both the specialist and the mainstream media offer a gateway to the public, stakeholders and policy makers, accessing new audiences and multiplying messages. Our media approach will range from electronic to printed media, targeting both news and feature pieces.

At the same time, chemical risk is a complex and sensitive issue and these factors affect the modalities of communicating with broader audiences. It will be important to reflect on the balance between the responsibility to communicate evidence of negative impacts on health and any possible negative impacts of raising public concern, in particular if the potential for change is limited. We will also need to decide when evidence is sufficiently robust to be communicated, and how we can clearly communicate any uncertainties in the evidence, as well as reflecting diverse opinions on the interpretation of evidence.

Ideally, an extensive database of regional, national and international media contacts should be built, to announce the start of the project, key events and results. Nevertheless, the European Environment Agency has a core network of journalists around Europe. In addition, we will work with the National Hubs to identify target media outlets in each partner country. All project partners are encouraged to contribute to media exposure at a regional and national level through their institutional PR departments.

Actions to secure media coverage include producing press releases and contributing to editorials, including through the provision of targeted materials and/or participation in interviews.

The Coordinator Team has been the main default contact for interested stakeholders, but WP3 is the main responsible for dealing with interview requests, yet each request will be assessed to check who

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 33

the most appropriate consortium member is to take up interviews, especially where specialisation is key.

A media kit will be designed and uploaded on the PARC website. A short Press and PR strategy with targets, activities and work plan will be after February 2023, which will be aligned with the social media strategy and the overall communication strategy. Content goes as follow:

1. Press clipping
2. Activities to liaise with communication departments of the partner's institutions to ensure a broad media coverage, if possible (including on-line briefing events with journalists)
3. Media Kit
4. Stories to pitch to the media towards the end of the project
5. List of magazines and non-specialised media (i.e., Horizon magazine, Research EU magazines, ...) and journalists (media database), bloggers and influencers as well as including national media in each partner country and National Hubs

13. Communication workplan

The 2022-23 communication plan is a dynamic document that is not fixed, but rather is updated throughout the year. Additional products, events and activities will be added, as the project develops.

Timeline	Communication products
October 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication and Dissemination Plan
November 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project identity designed (logo package, presentation and word templates for reports, deliverables, and letters as well as e-mail signature and event agenda, principal design for data visualization for figures and graphs, graphic roll out, etc.)
December 2022	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the PARC landing page • PARC leaflet • PARC Newsletter (or January) • Branding and Visual identity guidelines
January 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science Digest Newsletter • New updates on the PARC website
February 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science Digest Newsletter • Media Kit
March 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PARC Newsletter • Science Digest Newsletter • New updates on the PARC website (PARCOPEDIA)
May 2023	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science Digest Newsletter

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 34

A table like the one below will be completed together with the WPs co-leaders to include the products that we anticipate producing to communicate and disseminate based on the results that each work packages will produce in 2022-23. All deliverables will be included on the PARC website.

Results	Timing of results	Proposed communication products	Audiences

14. Risk communication

The risk communication strategy aims at widely disseminating the new knowledge produced in PARC while providing it with an “evergreen potential” while protecting it from misinformation and disinformation. Such valuable knowledge is expected to be information on the risks from specific chemicals and scientific evidence necessary for effective risk management decision making.

Risk communication within PARC can be seen as the interactive exchange of information and opinions among partners and the end users regarding risk analysis research results on chemical hazards and risks, risk-related factors and risk perceptions.

Risk communication strategy is dynamic as it requires input in the form of information about the nature and source of each chemical hazard in connection to risk, who or what is affected and how severely, the extent of exposure and the ability of individuals or public authorities to control the risk.

The PARC partners have to be engaged in dialogue with the end users of the project’s results, including policy makers and other stakeholders. Clear, straightforward, simplified messages need to be developed to raise awareness amongst the public, enabling public participation in the broader debate on chemicals while informing people about chemical safety.

Risk perception of all interested parties needs to be considered to facilitate understanding and dialogue amongst all interested parties. The valuable new knowledge produced in the project needs to be clear and accessible, including to people not directly involved in the process or laypersons not having a scientific background, while duly respecting the applicable legal provisions on confidentiality and protection of personal data.

Understanding information regarding chemicals from various sources (such as soil, wastewater, products, food), risks and safety is often an unconscious, cognitive process and it is influenced by motivational and emotional factors. Risk perception refers to beliefs, attitudes, judgments, and feelings; it is about opinions and it is influenced by multiple factors other than statistical calculation of risk. These are cognitive factors, emotional factors, socio-cultural factors and individual differences, as

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 35

well as demographics, personality dispositions and traits, past-experience, perceived benefit, heuristics etc.

Understanding the cognitive and decision-making processes is critical for overcoming the biases and the mental or conceptual frameworks people use to understand and evaluate risk and developing a strategy appropriately targeted and formulated.

One must keep in mind that perceived risk is inherently subjective and since risk cannot be measured independently of people’s minds and cultures, the notion of “real” or “objective” risk is not useful. This may imply a need for the segmentation of audiences and shift away from a one-size-fits-all approach (stakeholders, general public, experts, academic community etc.).

In relation to the expected outcomes of the PARC project the basic rules and guidelines of risk communication are the following:

- The scientific evidence is the basis of risk communication.
- Maintain integrity of information.
- Be clear, consistent and transparent.
- Consider your purpose and adopt messages to audience needs and expectations.
- Choose the most appropriate communication tools and channels depending on the PARC consortium’s objectives and the intended target audiences (e.g., based on Eurobarometer findings or dedicated surveys).
- Timely communication about the latest news and topics on project findings.
- Use of new tools to capture attention, especially to address non-specialist audiences
- Avoiding too much and mixed information in one single communication tool, but focusing on one key message per communication tool, namely “one chemical risk – one message”
- Careful design of campaigns (if chosen), to combine communication tools and channels to increase outreach and strengthen engagement
- When information is incomplete, state any uncertainties clearly.
- Setting KPIs to fine-tune the strategy

15. Monitoring and evaluation

Key indicators have been identified for PARC communication activities in order to measure the success of our activities and products. The impact indicators framework identified at Task 1.3 will be used, and these key indicators will ensure that the communication metrics align with the overall 1.3 indicator approach. The period for evaluation will be biannually.

See below the key indicators identified, which will be linked with the performance indicators identified under Tasks 1.3.

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 36

Activity	Metric	Explanation
PARC Website (same for PARC Microsite for citizens)	Unique visitors	The number of users requesting pages from the website during a given period, regardless of how often they visit
	Visits	The number of visits (or sessions) to a website
	Page views	Number of pages requested (also called Page Impressions)
	Return visit date	The Return Visit Rate is calculated as the number of visits from returning visitors divided by the total number of visits to the site. A high Return Visit Rate is a sign of high loyalty of the visitors
	Time spent per visit	The average amount of time spent per visit. Can serve as an indicator of interest
	Page views per visit	The average number of pages viewed per visit. Can serve as an indicator of interest
	Bounce rate	Bounce rate is defined as the percentage of visits that only has one page view before exit. A high bounce rate suggests that the content of the page is not relevant for the user/ the user cannot quickly find the information he/she need quickly enough....
	Conversation rate or goal completion rate	The percentage of visitors that complete a defined goal, such as signing up to a newsletter or download of a PDF
	Other information useful to know	Geographic location The sources (referrals) to the traffic to understand where the users are coming from: direct (typing the URL), referred (followed a link from another webpage), paid (banner or other ad), and social (link from a social platform).
Facebook	Page Likes	Total (accumulated) Page Likes
	Reach	Number of users that have been exposed to a page post (item) or any item related to the page.
	Engagement rate	The percentage of people who liked, commented, shared or clicked a post after having been exposed to it
You Tube	Total account views	Accumulated views for all videos published from the channel

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 37

	Unique Cookies	Like unique users, indicates how many people (devises) have viewed the video
	Estimated minutes watched	Accumulated estimated minutes watched on all videos
	Subscribers	Users subscribing to your YouTube channel
	Likes	All likes on all videos from your channel
	Comments	Shows how many comments are left on the videos
	Sharing	Shows how many times viewers share your videos and where
Instagram	Followers	Number of Instagram users following your account
	Likes received	Number of likes received on all posts
	Comments received	Number of likes received on all posts
Twitter	Followers	Number of Twitter users following the account
	Retweets	Total number of times tweets has been retweeted by other users
	Favourites	Total number of times tweets has been marked as a favourite by other users
	Impressions	Number of times a tweet was loaded onto a device's screen
	Engagement Rate	Any actions (including retweets and favourites) taken on a tweet, divided by the number of impressions this tweet received
LinkedIn	Impressions	How often has your post been seen
	Engagement (Rate)	The number of times users interacted with your post divided by the number of impressions this post received
	Reach	How often your updates have been seen daily
	Number of followers	Your total number of followers
PARC Newsletter same thing for the PARC Science Digest)	Subscribers	The number of people subscribed to the newsletter
	Unsubscribes	Number of people unsubscribing form the newsletter (An increased number of unsubscribers after a publication is an indicator of dissatisfaction with the newsletter)
	Open rate	The percentage of subscribers that open the newsletter
	Forward rate	The percentage of subscribers that forward the newsletter to friends/colleagues

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 38

	Bound rate	The percentage of mails not delivered because of closed email accounts, error in email address (Quality in subscribers' list)
	Click rate	The percentage of clicks that follow at least one link in the newsletter
	Conversation rate	The percentage of subscribers that perform the desired action. The number of visits and unique visitors. Also, which are the articles of most interest (most visited) and those of low interest as well as the time spent reading.
Events (conferences, workshops, webinars, PR events...)	Attendance	Attendance numbers from EU and national authorities, industry and NGOs, if possible.
	Number of collaborations	Number of collaborations potentially generated by the event
	Evaluation form	Comments and scoring in the evaluation form
	Number of presentations given	Number of presentations given in a conference
Reports	Open rate	The percentage of users that open the publication from the email
	Forward rate	The percentage of subscribers that forward the publication to friends/colleagues
	Bounce rate	The percentage of mails not delivered because of closed email accounts, error in mail address or the like
Peer reviewed publications	Number of publications	Number of scientific publications produced in PARC (to be discussed and approved by Task 3.1)
	Sum of the impact factor	All peer reviewed PARC publications are considered.
	Total number of citations	All peer reviewed PARC publications are considered. Self-citations are also involved.
Media coverage	Number of articles	Number of articles published in the media (international, national and local)
Communication products	Number of leaflets	Number of leaflets produced in PARC
	Number of videos	Number of videos produced in PARC
	Number of PARC Newsletters	Number of PARC Newsletters produced in PARC
	Number of PARC Science Digests	Number of PARC Science Digests produced in PARC
	Number of PARC Magazines	Number of PARC Magazines produced in PARC

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 39

	Number of policy briefs	Number of policy briefs produced in PARC
	Number of factsheets and infographics	Number of factsheets and infographics produced in PARC
	Number of research briefs	Number of research briefs produced in PARC
	Number of citizens	Number of citizens involved in the citizen survey
	Number of focus groups	Number of focus groups organised

In order to evaluate our communication products, we may additionally run surveys or online monitoring, or focus groups.

16. External communication rules, policies and procedures

Harmonized communication of the project outputs is a key element of success. The Partnership has many pathways for communication, running internally and externally. External communication takes place when PARC'S partners interact and communicate with stakeholders and entities outside the Partnership. It is important to regulate these channels for the sake of the Partnership interests. Communication policy and procedures need to be written out in a clear, straightforward and concise language for all involved parties to understand how they should act. External communication policy, procedures and rules aim to provide to the Consortium guidance for handling information in order to avoid liability issues and embarrassing or damaging situations for the Partnership that might risk our reputation. Communication tools that fall under the umbrella of external communication like press releases, website, social media posts, newsletters, etc, play a role in shaping the image and reputation of the Partnership, present and future collaborators and stakeholders.

16.1 Rules for external communication

By adopting formal rules regarding external communication of information, we ensure that PARC is in full control of desired public image and reputation. These rules should be updated if needed.

- **General**

EUROPEAN PARTNERSHIP

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 40

1. Before engaging in a communication or dissemination activity expected to have a major media impact, the CT must inform the granting authority. Furthermore, all affiliated entities must inform the national grant signatory at a national level.
2. If communicating on a matter on which the MB has taken a position, each member shall represent the views of the MB respecting the intended collegial approach sought in PARC. Members are free to give their own personal view but shall make clear that this does not necessarily represent the view of the MB.
3. Any published PARC communication products can be used in a national/regional level adapted to the national/regional needs.
4. Official language for communication will be English.
5. According to [European Commission guidelines](#) all dissemination materials issued by PARC have to include the EU emblem and acknowledgement.
6. The PARC logo should be included in all dissemination materials, including the website, brochures, flyers, presentations, roll-up, posters, both printed and online etc. A PARC branding ad visual identity guideline will be provided.
7. Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

- **Authorized Spokespersons**

With so much information coming into the Partnership, it may be a more efficient move to appoint authorized spokespersons to handle specific types of inquiries. A member of the MB with his/her alternate in close collaboration with WP(s) leaders should be authorized to properly handle communication at EU level with local media, while the NHCP should play the same role at a national/regional level. The chosen spokespersons can delegate their role to the appropriate WP leader if a more specific or accurate information is needed, thus organizing and streamlining information sharing.

- **Press Releases**

Press releases should go out anytime the Partnership has something important to announce, as they are the best way to pass the desired message to the general public or any other entity, and they can be very versatile. Press releases can be helpful for communicating with media outlets, you can also publish them online or post them on social media.

A press release should be approved by the Coordination Team at consortium level or by the NHCP at a national level, at least 3 working days before publication.

- **Newsletters, website and social media**

Two newsletters/year will be issued by PARC in English. The material to be included in the newsletter will be proposed/prepared by the WPs leaders, checked for compliance with the communication rules and the PARC communication objectives by the WP3.

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D3.2: Communication and Dissemination Strategy	Dissemination level: PU
WP3: Synergies, collaborations and awareness	Version: 2.0
Main Authors: Tamás Szigeti and Roser Gasol	Page: 41

Social media accounts as well as the website content will be managed by WP3. Specific PARC hashtags should be used in all social media posts.

16.2 Policies for external communication

The communication plan will be updated and will always ensure to manage communication with the target audience following GDPR rules.

Communication activities would draw the attention (general and specialised audiences) to the EU policy areas addressed (Green Deal - One substance one assessment).

All communication activities will further promote and respect gender equality.

Open access policy will be followed for the dissemination.

17. Internal communication plan

The internal communication plan will be included in the PARC's Handbook, as part of the 4.5 section on communication and dissemination of results.

In this section, the internal communication procedures will be explained, rules and recommendations for a correct use of the external communication tools, working templates. Other information such as how to produce and collect content from the partners, including news for the website, how to track and communicate attendance in conferences and workshops, or how to fill in the internal newsletter template will also be part of that section.

In the PARC's Handbook, the mechanisms that will be used throughout the project in order to ensure the quality level will also be described.

The role of the WP3 in cooperation with the CT is crucial to ensure an efficient, coordinated and harmonized communication among all PARC partners during the project life.

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